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NANOFACTS
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“NETWORKING ACTIVITIES FOR NANOTECHNOLOGY-FACILITATED CANCER
THERANOSTICS”

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1. Overview

Cancer represents a significant health challenge in Europe. The application of nanotechnology in medicine offers new opportunities to overcome the drawbacks of conventional therapy and develop optimized therapeutic and diagnostic tools. The NANOFACTS training school provided a transfer of knowledge from international experts to Ph.D. students, researchers, and young professionals on scientific advances related to the development of microfluidic, magnetic, and optical biosensors for cancer, as well as in the development of nanomaterials for targeted therapy and imaging of cancer. Clinical and surgical aspects of cancer treatment and new knowledge about cancer biomarkers were also conveyed during the sessions. In addition, lectures aiming to enhance the basic skills of researchers, such as creative thinking, teamwork, and problem-solving skills will be provided. Finally, lectures related to writing scientific project proposals, project implementation, and startup management were aimed at enhancing the self-sustainability of researchers.

The Training school (TS) was organized by BIOS, during the week of 27th June – 1st July 2022. First three days included the TS lectures (TSLs) at Science & Technology Park, Novi Sad. The fourth and fifth day of the TS event included Workshops (WSs) and Workshop lectures (WSLs), which were organized at the Rectorate building of the University of Novi Sad and at the laboratories of the Biosense institute.

Participation at the event was free of charge after registration through the Nanofacts website (nanofacts.net).

The event was advertised through different channels: electronic (news media, website and social groups) and printed (posters and leaflets). A dedicated webpage for the event was established at the following address: <https://www.nanofacts.net/training-school/>. All dissemination activities of the event included a unique schematic which was produced specifically for the event. Figure 1 represent schematic which was used for dissemination through Facebook.

Figure 1 Schematic for dissemination of the NANOFACTS Training school through Facebook.

The TS was organized in the following manner:

The first day of lectures included introduction of the NANOFACETS agenda and topics that are relevant for construction of cancer-related biosensors.

The second day of the TS included topics of relevance to the development of cancer theranostic nanomaterials, as well as the clinical and surgical aspects of cancer treatment.

The TSLs on the third day included topics of relevance to the development of “basic skills” of researchers, such as creative thinking, teamwork and problem-solving skills, followed by the lectures in project writing, project management, and startup creation and management.

The fourth day of the TS event included Workshops and WSLs on the topics relevant to cancer-related biosensing and cancer theranostic nanomaterials.

The fifth day was dedicated to WSLs and WSLs in cancer theranostic nanomaterials.

2. Training school lectures (TSLs) in Cancer Theranostic Nanomaterials

During the second day of the TS lectures, 7 lectures were organized. Two lecturers (Dr. Oliviero Gobbo and Dr. Binh T. Mai) are members of NANOFACETS consortium while 5 lecturers are invited external speakers. During the second day, in total 49 persons attended the lectures. Of this number, 13 attendees are employed at BIOS, 25 are young scientists (junior researchers and students) and 24 are experienced researchers.

2.1. TSL: Design of magnetic nanoarchitectures for cancer theranostics

The lecture was held by Prof. Dr. Davide Peddis, an Associate Professor of Physical chemistry at the University of Genova and associate researcher at CNR-ISM (Figure 2).

Date & Time: June 28th, 2022. 09:30 – 10:25

Figure 2 Lecture of Prof. Davide Peddis

Abstract:

Design of magnetic nanoarchitectures for cancer theranostics

Davide Peddis

Università di Genova-Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica industriale, Via
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CNR-ISM, Area della Ricerca Roma 1, Via Salaria km 29.300, C.P. 10, 00016 Monterotondo
Scalo (RM), Italy

Magnetic Nanoparticles (MNPs) are unique complex objects whose physical properties differ greatly from their parent bulk materials. In fact, the magnetic properties are particularly sensitive to the particle size, being determined by finite size effects on the core properties, related to the reduced number of spins cooperatively linked within the particle, and by surface effects, becoming more important as the particle size decreases. [1–3] MNPs play an important role in nature, as they are commonly found in soils, sediments and rocks and may store information on the past Earth's magnetic field as well as environmental conditions at the time of sediment deposition. In addition, magnetic nanoparticles have generated much interest because of their possible applications in high density data storage, ferrofluid technology, catalysis and biomedicine (drug delivery, contrast enhanced MRI). Design of magnetic nano-architecture (MNA) for specific applications means to control the matter at the nanoscale, correlating magnetic properties, micro- and meso-structure and molecular coating. These MNA are typically of core-shell morphology, with a magnetic core and a shell that may be composed of polymers surfactants or mesoporous silica, which typically serve for embedding the therapeutic agents within their framework. Selectivity of the treatment is ensured through employing magnetic field responsive homing of the nanocarriers to the therapeutic area, along with possibilities for alternating magnetic field hyperthermia-resulted treatment of the ill tissues. The induced hyperthermia may be therapeutically active through causing denaturation of biomolecules in the treatment area, or/and through mediating release of the cargo therapeutic agents. Taking into account all of these points, this communication will focus on the design MNA for application in biomedicine discussing some recent results synthesis and functionalization of magnetic nanomaterials[4–6].

- [1] D. Peddis, Magnetic Properties of Spinel Ferrite Nanoparticles : Influence of the Magnetic Structure, in: K.N. Trohidou (Ed.), Magn. Nanoparticle Assem., Pan Stanford Publishing, Singapore, 2014: pp. 978–981.
- [2] D. Peddis, N. Yaacoub, M. Ferretti, A. Martinelli, G. Piccaluga, A. Musinu, C. Cannas, G. Navarra, J.M. Greneche, D. Fiorani, Cationic distribution and spin canting in CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter.* 23 (2011) 426004. doi:<http://stacks.iop.org/0953-8984/23/i=42/a=426004>.
- [3] D. Peddis, P.E. Jonsson, G. Varvaro, S. Laureti, Magnetic Interactions: A Tool to Modify the Magnetic Properties of Materials Based on Nanoparticles, in: C. Binns (Ed.), Nanomagnetism Fundam. Appl., Elsevier B.V, Oxford, UK, 2014: pp. 129–189.
- [4] A. Scano, V. Cabras, F. Marongiu, D. Peddis, M. Piloni, New opportunities in the preparation of nanocomposites for biomedical applications: revised mechanosynthesis of magnetite-silica nanocomposites, *Mater. Res. Express.* 4 (2017) 025004. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1591/aa5867>.
- [5] C. Scialabba, R. Puleio, D. Peddis, G. Varvaro, P. Calandra, G. Cassata, L. Cicero, M. Licciardi, G. Giammona, Folate targeted coated SPIONs as efficient tool for MRI, *Nano Res.* 5 (2017) 1–16. doi:<http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s12274-017-1540-4>.
- [6] G. Singh, B.H. McDonagh, S. Hak, D. Peddis, S. Bandopadhyay, I. Sandvig, A. Sandvig, W.R. Glomm, Synthesis of gadolinium oxide nanodisks and gadolinium doped iron oxide nanoparticles for MR contrast agents, *J. Mater. Chem. B.* 5 (2017) 418–422. doi:<http://xlink.rsc.org/?DOI=C6TB02854C>.

2.2. TSL: Cancer prevention using magnetic nanoparticles

The lecture was held by Dr. Oliviero Gobbo, a Senior Research Fellow at Trinity College Dublin. (Figure 3).

Date & Time: June 28th, 2022. 10:25 – 11:20

Figure 3 Lecture by Dr. Oliviero Gobbo

Abstract

This lecture was composed of two parts. The first part presented examples of theranostic nanoparticles for pathologies such as cancer or neurodegenerative diseases (e.g. Parkinson's disease). It presented the potential advances offered by nanomedicine. It included a combination stem cells, natural materials (e.g. chitosan and clathrin), reactive structures, shRNA, neurotrophic factor antibodies and superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPION).

The second part presented a detailed description of the use of theranostic nanoparticles to prevent cancer through the destruction of visceral fat. Indeed, adiposopathy, defined as a pathological function of adipose tissue, is promoted and exacerbated by the accumulation of fat in overweight and obese patients, which causes the most common metabolic diseases such as type 2 diabetes, hypertension and heart disease. But it is also responsible for certain types of cancer.

The generation of mechanical forces via magnetic fields, known as the magneto-mechanical effect, is a powerful tool for manipulating SPIONs in varying environments. Functionalised SPIONs specifically target adipocytes and induce cell damage by exerting magneto-mechanical stresses. Their preliminary results have shown that the magneto-mechanical effect influences adipocytes in in vitro experiments. However, it is not clear whether SPIONs destroy cells or induce fatty acid release from adipocytes. It is therefore apparent that this approach can reduce visceral fat and thus lower adiposity-induced cancers.

2.3. TSL: Multifunctional nanoparticles for cancer imaging

The lecture was held by Dr. Jelena Zinnanti, a staff scientist at Max Planck Institute for Intelligent Systems, Stuttgart, Germany (Figure 4).

Date & Time: June 28th, 2022. 11:20 – 12:15

Figure 4 Lecture by Dr. Jelena Zinnanti

Abstract

Non-invasive and non-ionizing imaging modalities, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), offer great diagnostic capabilities in cancer detection. Despite good resolution and excellent soft tissue contrast, very little can be inferred about the cancerous tissue itself, such as metabolic activity, or extent of neoangiogenesis. Possibility to non-invasively evaluate such features would not only benefit in assessing malignant potential, but aid in better monitor of the treatment efficacy as well. In this talk, dr. Zinnanti introduced functionalized superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) aimed at non-invasive imaging of neo-angiogenesis and tumor metabolism. In-vivo animal model of glioblastoma (U87) and glioma (PTEN knockout) were used in combination with MR imaging. For imaging of neoangiogenesis, SPION particles functionalized with GX1 or GX1-RGD peptide are developed, based on interaction of GX1 with TGM-2 receptor on endothelial cells, upregulated in many cancers. Areas of accumulation of SPION-GX1 particles, measured by quantitative decrease in transverse relaxivity time (T_2), were found to coincide with areas of increased neoangiogenesis (CD34 staining, immunohistochemistry). For imaging of metabolic activity, SPIONs functionalized with 2D glucose are developed. Increased SPION-2D glucose accumulation (measured by decrease in T_2 time), was found to coincide with metabolically active tumor regions as opposed to necrotic regions (no accumulation was measured). As expected glioblastoma accumulated more SPION-2D glucose particles compared to glioma, due to their increased metabolic rates in response to faster progression. In addition, application of SPION-2D glucose could be used to distinguish tumor inflammation, induced by IL-2, from active tumor regions. Lastly, some recent developments and potential use of SPION particles in localized and on-demand drug delivery during MRI were introduced and discussed.

2.4. TSL: Clinical aspects of cancer treatment

The lecture was held by Dr. Igor Djan, medical doctor at the Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Novi Sad (Figure 5).

Date & Time: June 28th, 2022. 13:30 – 14:25

Figure 5 Lecture by dr. Igor Djan

Abstract

Clinical procedures for the treatment of patients diagnosed with brain cancer Glioblastoma Multiforme (GBM) were described. Tumor markers associated with GBM were also discussed. GBM is the most aggressive primary brain tumor. Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) gene polymorphisms and overexpression are involved in high-grade malignant gliomas. The aim of the study of dr. Djan was to assess the distribution of +405C>G VEGF gene polymorphism in patients diagnosed by glioblastoma and to test its association with the overall survival (OS). The associations of the observed genotypes and clinical data were evaluated. Results: The most frequent single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) variant was G (72.58%). The GG genotype was proved to have statistically significant longer OS and patient status (alive/dead) compared to CC and CG genotypes ($p=0.022$ and 0.005 , respectively). Conclusion: their results indicate that +405C>G VEGF gene polymorphism may be used as prognostic genetic marker of OS in GBM patients. In addition, the of dr. Djan showed that concomitant usage of temozolomide and radiotherapy was beneficial in the treatment of GBM, and statistically significant difference among groups and subgroups was observed regarding overall survival.

2.5. TSL: Radiolabeled nanoparticles for the application in diagnosis and cancer treatment

The lecture was held by Dr. Sanja Vranješ Djurić, Research professor, Head of the Laboratory for radioisotopes of the Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, University of Belgrade, Serbia (Figure 7).

Date & Time: June 28th, 2022. 14:25 – 15:20

Figure 6 Lecture by dr. Vranješ-Djurić

Abstract

Radiolabeled nanoparticles (NPs) are finding an increasing interest in a broad range of biomedical applications. They may be used to detect and characterize diseases, to deliver relevant therapeutics and to study the pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic parameters of nanomaterials. The use of radiotracer techniques in the research of novel nanoparticles offer many advantages but there are still some limitations. The binding of radionuclides to nanoparticles has to be irreversible in order to prevent their escape to other tissues or organs. Due to the half-life of radionuclides, the manufacturing process is time-limited and difficult, and there is also a risk of contamination. Dr. Vranješ-Djurić presented the main selection criteria for radionuclides and applicable radiolabeling procedures used for the radiolabeling of various nanoparticles. Also, an overview of different types of NPs that have so far been labeled with radionuclides was presented.

The selection criteria for radionuclides must be based on the physical data about the radionuclide and biological variables governing their use. The considerations for physical characteristics include the physical half-life, type of emissions, energy of the radiation, daughter

product, method of production, and radionuclide purity. The biochemical aspects include tissue targeting, the retention of radioactivity in the organ/tissue, in vivo stability, and toxicity.

Diagnostic radionuclides are generally short-lived radionuclides capable to provide the necessary information on biodistribution, dosimetry, and the limiting or the critical organ or the tissue. Radionuclides for SPECT imaging decay by the emission of high-energy photons, while PET radionuclides decay by emission of positrons. The selection of appropriate therapeutic radionuclides that emit α - or β - particles depends upon the nature, the extent, and stage of disease. These types of particulate radiations allow very high ionization per length of travel. Therefore, they are fully deposited within a small range of tissue (usually in mm). The longer range of beta particles can still permit uniform tumor irradiation despite a possible heterogeneity of distribution of radioactivity within the tumor. Therapeutic radionuclides which also decay with γ -radiation can be advantageous if the energy and intensity are within the diagnostic range, as it provides the ability to visualize distribution of the radiolabeled NPs.

2.6. TSL: The combined use of hydrogels and nanoparticles for the treatment of brain tumors

The lecture was held by Dr. Binh T. Mai, Postdoctoral scholar at Trinity College Dublin (Figure 7).

Date & Time: June 28th, 2022. 15:20 – 16:15

Figure 7 Lecture by dr. Binh Mai

Abstract

Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is a high-grade brain tumour, showing a poor prognosis and low response to conventional treatments such as surgery, chemotherapy, and radiation therapy. With a high mortality rate of 90 - 95% recorded within 5 years of diagnosis, there is an urgent need to develop more efficient treatments to tackle this challenging cancer. The blood brain barrier (BBB) is one of the main challenges in GBM as it suppresses the delivery of therapeutic agents to the tumour lesion. To overcome this issue, the use of local therapy in which the therapeutic agents are

administered directly at the tumor lesion represents an interesting alternative approach. In this context, injectable hydrogel and nanoparticles are among the most intriguing candidates. Injectable hydrogels have been used for decades for drug delivery applications as they offer the possibility to stabilize loaded drug molecules and allow for their long retention at the tumor site upon intratumoral injection. On the other hand, nanoparticle represents an interesting platform for drug delivery as they can load drug and enable them to cross different biological barriers, thus maximizing their therapeutic performance. In addition, NPs' surface can be tethered or coated with specific ligand, enabling them to target cancer cell and spare the healthy tissues. Notably, hydrogels and nanoparticles can be tailored in such a way that they can respond to the tumor microenvironment, leading to a programmable release feature which is highly desirable for the controlled delivery of different chemotherapy. This lecture focused on an overview on the characteristics of GBM, the challenges in their management and the state-of-the-art hydrogel-nanoparticles systems that have been used to treat GBM. It also covered different types of promising stimuli-responsive nanoparticles and hydrogels that might be found for their potential in battling this challenging disease.

2.7. TSL: Emergency surgery – new technology

The lecture was held by Dr. Srdjan Mijatović, Medical doctor, a specialist in urgent surgery at the Clinical centre of Serbia (Figure 8).

Date & Time: June 28th, 2022. 16:15 – 17:00

Figure 8 Lecture by dr. Srdjan Mijatović

Abstract

Methodologies for performing urgent surgery of cancer and laparoscopic surgery were covered. Novel methodologies which enable performing long-range surgery through the use of robotic assistance were conveyed, which open substantial opportunities for future development of surgery.

3. Workshop lectures (WSLs) in Cancer Theranostic Nanomaterials

During the fifth day of the TS week, 3 WS lectures were organized. Two lecturers (Prof. Maria Santos-Martinez and Dr. Oliviero Gobbo) are members of NANOFACTS consortium while 1 WS lecturer (dr. Thi Nga Tran) is and invited external speaker. During the fifth day, in total 30 persons attended the WS lectures. Of this number, 23 attendees are employed at BIOS, 12 are young scientists (junior researchers and students) and 18 are experienced researchers.

3.1 WSL: Nanosafety and the Regulatory Landscape (online lecture)

The lecture was held by Prof. Dr. Maria Santos-Martinez, an Associate Professor at Trinity College Dublin. (Figure 9).

Date & Time: July 1st, 2022. 09:00 – 09:45

Figure 9 Online lecture by Prof. Dr. Maria Santos-Martinez

Abstract

Nanomaterials have multiple physical and chemical properties that make them very attractive for their potential use in medicine for diagnosis or therapeutic purposes. However, although those properties may be beneficial from the theoretical point of view for many medical applications, they may be also responsible for potential harmful effects. Humans and the environment may become exposed to nanomaterials not only during their intended used but also during their production and disposal and therefore, the potential impact of the exposure to engineered nanomaterials is under continuous investigation. WHO recognises that manufactured nanomaterials can induce health problems and that their potential toxicity may largely depend on their physicochemical properties. Dr Santos-Martinez discussed some of those facts during her talk, presented the guidelines

published by WHO in this regard and the role and publications available from the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) in the US. Then, she focused on the regulations of nanomaterials in Europe, the role of the Joint Research Centre (JRC) and presented as well some of the guidelines and publications available on this matter in both, Europe and Ireland.

Although it is widely known that depending on their size, charge, shape or composition, nanoparticles may exert toxic effects at different levels, she highlighted that the risks associated to their routes of entry and the molecular mechanisms involved on those potential cytotoxic effects need to be better understood. At the end of her talk, she focused on the importance of characterising nanoparticles under relevant biological environments and the significance of testing the blood compatibility of nanoparticles, ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects and the role of GDPR on ethics applications.

3.2 WSL: Designing Animal Experiments

The lecture was held by Dr. Oliviero Gobbo, a Senior Research Fellow at Trinity College Dublin. (Figure 10).

Date & Time: July 1st, 2022. 09:45 – 10:30

Figure 10 WSL by dr. Oliviero Gobbo

Abstract

This lecture provided a brief history of the use of animals in research and explained how they have always been necessary to understand biology and produce treatments for human and animal diseases. A large part of the lecture was devoted to ethics and the different theories of animal protection. Dr. Gobbo explained in detail why Russell and Burch's "3Rs" (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement) are used in modern research when animals are used. Videos of rodent experiments are used to illustrate this objective. Alternatives to animal experimentation are also proposed with their advantages and problems. Examples from dr. Gobbo's research are given to explain how to organise animal experiments before they start (e.g. applying for a licence for the animals and

discussing with the animal research ethics committee) and how the animals are constantly monitored to ensure their welfare. Finally, the lecture highlighted the importance of biostatistics in animal research in order to reduce the number of animals and still be able to detect an effect when there is one to be detected. This lecture did not promote animal experimentation, but presented an objective view of the use of animals in research.

3.3 WSL: Sustainable CO₂-based biocomposites for active food packaging and biomedical applications

The workshop lecture was held by Dr. Thi Nga Tran, a Postdoctoral fellow at University of Limerick. (Figure 11).

Date & Time: July 1st, 2022. 14:00 – 14:45

Figure 11 WSL of dr. Thi Nga Tran

Abstract

To tackle the global warming issue and achieve a climate neutral world by 2050, a primary mission of United Nations sustainable development goals is the reducing of CO₂ emission. The advanced technology to exploit CO₂ as a renewable and advantageous carbon source to produce biodegradable polymeric materials is an intriguing and sustainable approach. This will help to reduce CO₂ emission and simultaneously substitute of nonbiodegradable, petroleum-based plastics with biodegradable plastics. Poly(propylene carbonate) (PPC), a carbon dioxide (CO₂) derived polymer, offers various advantages including high transparency, great flexibility, high barrier and biodegradability. However, PPC shows some drawback of relative low glass transition temperature, mechanical strength, and thermal stability. In this lecture, the effect of nano- and micro-fillers on the improved properties of PPC-based biocomposites. Furthermore, the applications of these renewable and low carbon footprint materials made of PPC for active food packaging and biomedical areas were discussed.

4. Workshop (WS) in Cancer Theranostic Nanomaterials

4.1 WS: In vitro assessment of therapeutic nanomaterials in 2D and 3D cell cultures

The workshop was held by Dr. Amelia Ultimo, a Postdoctoral fellow at Trinity College Dublin. (Figure 12).

The workshop was organized in two parts, the first part on Thursday, June 30th and the second part on Friday, July 1st 2022. The first part of the workshop was attended by 25 researchers from the Biosense institute while on the second day there were 23 attendees employed at BIOS.

Date & Time: June 30th, 2022. 09:00-11:00 and July 1st, 2022. 10:30 – 12:30

Figure 12 WS and WSL by dr. Amelia Ultimo

Abstract

The basic aim of this workshop was to show the students and researchers involved in the project basic handling techniques in a cell culture laboratory in the context of the validation of nanoparticle-based drug delivery systems.

During the first of the two sessions, therefore, the basic rules necessary to be followed in this type of environment in order to maintain sterility and to ensure proper handling of cell samples have been explained. Afterwards, the participants have been shown how to keep the cells in culture, how to transfer them to grow, and how to count and seed them in the different types of plates required for the different experiments that are generally carried out as part of the in vitro assessment of nanoparticle-based drug delivery systems. Both two-dimensional and three-dimensional cellular systems, the spheroids, were shown.

In the second practical session in the laboratory, participants were shown how cells seeded the previous day had adhered and multiplied in the plates, or how spheroids had formed. Furthermore, the students and researchers present were taught how to transfer the spheroids from the low-attachment plates in which they grew, to other kinds of the slides for further analysis without damaging their shape and integrity.

At the same time, a short theoretical presentation of the techniques commonly used in the validation of nanoparticle-based drug delivery systems, their usefulness and the information that can be derived from them was given to the participants to complete the training on in vitro techniques.

Equipment used:

Biological safety cabinet, Aspirator, Incubator, Optical microscope, Centrifuge

4.2 WS: Preparation of composite biomaterials for biomedical application

The workshop was conducted by Dr. Thi Nga Tran, a Postdoctoral fellow at University of Limerick.

Date & Time: July 1st, 2022. 08:30-09:00 and 14:45 – 15:45

The workshop was attended by 23 researchers from the Biosense institute.

Description

This workshop was planned to be conducted in two parts. The first part was conducted in the morning of July 1st, where dr. Thi Nga prepared the composite biomaterials with the help of Nejra Omerovic, a PhD student from BIOS.

These biomaterials contained biodegradable polymers with encapsulated cinnamon and curcumin inside the films. The second part of the WS was planned to be conducted also by Dr Thi Nga in the afternoon, after her WSL, which would be used to demonstrate the degradability of the prepared biocomposite films in the conditions of different pH values and the release of bioactive compounds. However, due to Covid-19 concerns and the fact that these demonstrations were intended to be conducted in a narrow space of the laboratory at the Biosense institute, in the presence of numerous researchers, the second part of the WS was conducted online.

For this purpose, dr. Thi Nga filmed the preparation of the biocomposite materials at the BIOS laboratory and then she explained and introduced the preparation steps and the concept for this WS during her WSL (Figure 13). The attendees were also able to see the final biocomposite materials in the BIOS lab, after the WSL and Nejra Omerovic helped in clarifying any issues, as she was helping dr. Thi Nga to prepare the WS demonstration before her arrival and during the first part of the WS.

Figure 13. WS presentation by dr. Thi Nga

Annex I: List of participants during the TSLs in cancer theranostic nanomaterials

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 28. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
1.	Ivana Podunavac	researcher	BioSense
2.	СТЕПАН ЖАРКОВИЋ	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
3.	marino kornis	PROFESSOR	UNIGO
4.	Aleksandar Jabrović	Junior Research Assistant	BIOSENSE
5.	VALE FRIZIJA	PROFESSOR	INL
6.	Oli Gobbo	Researcher	TCD
7.	BINH MAI	Researcher	TCD
8.	Miroslav Đocos	Student	FTN
9.	Marisa Vejin,	student	FTN
10.	Marisa Milanovic	professor	Faculty of Technology, UNS
11.	Ljiljana Hubrović	Student	PMF
12.	Đurađ Radončić	Student	PMF
13.	Ivan Bobinetskiy	researcher	Biosense
14.	Борис Крстичевић	senior res.	INN VINČA
15.	SANJA KRANJEŠ-ĐURID	SENIOR RES.	INN VINČA
16.	IRENA MILER	RESEARCHER	BioSense
17.	BORIS POPOVIĆ	Full professor	Faculty of Agriculture
18.	Ružica Đuro Pivović	researcher	Faculty of Agriculture
19.	Teodora Kutrić	junior researcher	Faculty of Agriculture
20.	Ksenija Đurđev	student	Faculty of Science
21.	Jelena Kijac	student	Faculty of Science

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACETS 28. 6. 2022.

22.	Peter ERTL	Prof	TU Vienna
23.	GIUSEPPE SPOTO	PROFESSOR	UNIV. CATANIA
24.	Сретенка Ђурић	Researcher	BioSense
25.	Marko Tamić	RESEARCHER	Bio Sense
26.	BILJANA ŠAVIĆ	FOOD ENGINEERING PHD RE STUDENT	FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY NOVI SAD
27.	Flavia Barbero Roccio	Researcher	PLASTORE
28.	FRANCESCO FLORIS	RESEARCHER	PLASTORE
29.	Nina Eutović	student	FTN
30.	Jelena Đerić	student	FTN
31.	Sandra Jajić	student	FTN
32.	JELENA RADEVIĆ	STUDENT	FACULTY OF SCIENCES
33.	GIORANA ILIĆ	STUDENT	FACULTY OF SCIENCES
34.	Teodora Despotovski	student	Faculty of Sciences
35.	Čestimir Čelebić	senior researcher	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE
36.	Nikolina Janković	Researcher	BioSense Institute
37.	Nevena Jakić	student	Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade
38.	Milica Pena	student	Faculty of Sciences
39.	Neja Omerović	junior researcher	BioSense Institute
40.	Zorica Novaković	Student	PMF
41.	Mila Đisalo	Junior research assistant	BioSense Institute
42.	MINJA MLADENOVIĆ	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE
43.	Sara Joksović	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BioSense Institute

ATTENDANCE LIST

Training school NANOFACETS 28. 6. 2022.

44.	Petar Davidovic	RESEARCH ASSISTANT	FACULTY OF SCIENCES UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SARAJEVO
45.	Jelena Zinnanti	STUFF SCIENTIST	MAX PLANCK INSTITUTE Stuttgart, Germany
46.	Igor Đah	MD IRRADIATION analyst	IOV S. Kragujevac
47.	Sanja Kojic	TEACHING ASSISTANT	Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad
48.	Veljko Đukić	Senior Research Associate	FTM, Belgium
49.	Miroslav Kvesić	SENIOR RESEARCHER	BIO
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Annex II: List of participants during the first day of the WS in cancer theranostic nanomaterials

ATTENDANCE LIST Training school NANOFACETS 30. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
1.	AMELIA UJTIMO	RESEARCHER	TCD
2.	O. Cobbo	Researcher	TCD
3.	Ivana Podunavac	Junior researcher	BioSense
4.	Nejra Omerović	Junior researcher	BioSense Institute
5.	СТЕПАН ЈАРЛУЊ	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
6.	Nevena Jaćimović	Student	Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade
7.	Mila Đisalo	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BioSense Institute
8.	Bara Joršević	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BioSense Institute
9.	Aleksandra Jakić	Junior research assistant	BioSense Institute
10.	Nikolina Janković	Researcher	BioSense
11.	IRENA MILER	Researcher	BioSense
12.	Ivan Bobinec	researcher	BIOSENSE
13.	FRANCESCO FLORII	Researcher	PLASTORE
14.	FRANCESCO FLORII	RESEARCHER	PLASTORE
15.	George Dubois	Researcher BioSense	
16.	Olivera Djurđević	Junior Research Assistant	Olivera
17.	MINJA MADENOVIĆ	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE
18.	Andreja Čelić	Junior researcher	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE
19.	Maril Kukkar	Researcher	BioSense
20.	MARKO PANIĆ	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
21.	MARKO PANIĆ	Researcher	BioSense

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACETS 30. 6. 2022.

22.	Dusan Žilbović	Student	PMF
23.	Nikola Kavran	SENIOR RESEARCHER	BIOS
24.	Čedomir Čalić	senior researcher	BIOS
25.	Milena Janković	Researcher	BIOS
26.	Željko Bujutić	Other	BIOS
27.	Mama Džajić	Researcher	BIOS
28.	Alma Nikrović	Researcher	BIOS
29.	Herman Kuman R-D	Researcher	BIOS
30.	Al.	RESEARCHER	BIOS
31.	Tomislav	RESEARCHER	BIOS
32.	Branimir	RESEARCHER	BIOS
33.	Jan Ožek	RESEARCHER	BIOS
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Annex III: List of participants during the WSLs and the second day of the WS in cancer theranostic nanomaterials

ATTENDANCE LIST Training school NANOFACETS 1. 7. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
1.	Nevena Jačimović	Student	Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade
2.	AMELIA ULTIMO	RESEARCHER	TCD
3.	O. Gobbo	Researcher	TCD
4.	ОТЕРАНА ЈАКУШ	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOS
5.	Ivana Podunavac	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOS
6.	Teodora Knežić	Junior Researcher	BIOS
7.	Mila Đisalo	Junior Research assistant	BioSense
8.	Ivan Gubrinetsky	Researcher	BioSense
9.	Crabbeys Celest	Junior Researcher	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE
10.	Nikola Knežević	SENIOR RESEARCHER	BIOS
11.	Thi Nga Tran	Researcher	University of Limerick
12.	Uleja Omerović	Junior researcher	BioSense Institute
13.	IRENA MILER	RESEARCHER	BioSense
14.	Dusan Živković	Student	PMF
15.	MARIA BARBARA PACCIONI	Researcher	PLASTORE
16.	FRANCESCO FLORIS	RESEARCHER	PLASTORE
17.	дејана чижуби	Junior Research Assistant	Biosense
18.	А. Табош	Junior Research Assistant	Biosense
19.	Nikolina Janković	Researcher	Biosense
20.	Georges Dubourg	Researcher	Biosense
21.	Melena Janković	Researcher	BIOS

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACETS 1. 7. 2022.

22.	<i>Jozse Byntr</i>	Other	BIOS
23.	<i>Milica Djedich</i>	Researcher	BIOS
24.	<i>Mina Minovic</i>	Researcher	BIOS
25.	<i>Herman Kuman R.R</i>	Researcher	BIOS
26.	<i>J.H.</i>	RESEARCHER	BIOS
27.	<i>Josy cy</i>	RESEARCHER	BIOS
28.	<i>Branco Bogic</i>	RESEARCHER	BIOS
29.	<i>Sara Joksovic</i>	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BioSense Institute
30.	<i>Am Oka</i>	RESEARCHER	BIOS
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